

Spray Tower showed that cypermethrin, fenvalerate, and carbosulfan were the most toxic, and endosulfan the least toxic (Table 1). For phosalone, a tenfold difference in LC50 values existed between 4-hour and 48-hour exposures.

Carbaryl, phosphamidon, phosalone, quinalphos, endosulfan, chlorpyrifos, isofenphos, fenthion, thiometon, fenitrothion, dimethoate, and phenthoate were relatively less toxic.

Translocation of insecticide applied to foliage was measured by shielding the lower portion of test plants and spraying the upper foliage. BPH nymphs were confined to the lower unsprayed portion. Of 9 insecticides evaluated, BPMC exhibited downward translocation but the effect did not persist beyond 5 days. Chlorpyrifos, isofenphos, dicrotophos,

Table 1. Contact toxicity of selected insecticides against brown planthopper nymphs (Potters Spray Tower method) at Hyderabad, India.

Insecticide	LC ₅₀	
	After 4 h	After 48 h
Cypermethrin	0.0052	0.0061
Fenvalerate	0.0089	0.0070
Carbosulfan	0.0123	0.0101
Permethrin	0.0667	0.0389
BPMC	0.0864	0.0408
Monocrotophos	0.0814	0.0426
Phosalone	0.243	0.0210
Quinalphos	0.225	0.147
Endosulfan	0.299	0.151

carbofuran, monocrotophos, demeton-O-methyl, carbaryl, and MIPC did not show appreciable translocation.

To evaluate ovicidal activity, spray formulations (0.05%) were tested on

Table 2. Ovicidal activity of selected insecticides at Hyderabad, India.

Insecticide (0.05% spray)	Hatching (%)
Carbosulfan	0
MIPC	0
BPMC	0
Knockbal	1
Phosalone	9
Isofenphos	7
Carbaryl	7
Monocrotophos	13
Cypermethrin	58
Fenvalerate	67
Untreated control	83

1-day-old BPH eggs. Carbosulfan, MIPC, BPMC, knockbal, carbaryl, isofenphos, phosalone, and monocrotophos had the highest ovicidal activity. Cypermethrin and fenvalerate were poor ovicidal agents (Table 2).

Synthetic pyrethroids for controlling leaffolders on rice

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Three synthetic pyrethroids for controlling rice leaffolders, a treated control (fenthion 500 g a.i./ha), and an untreated control were studied during 1980-81 samba (July-August to November-December). The field trial was laid out in a randomized complete block design with nine treatments and three replications. Chemicals were sprayed at 15, 30, and 45 days after transplanting (DT) IR8.

Controlling rice leaffolders by synthetic pyrethroids in Tirur, India.

Treatment	Formulation	Dosage per application (g a.i./ha)	Leaf damage (%) 60 DT	Grain yield (t/ha)
Cypermethrin	10 IC	25	27.30	3.65
Cypermethrin	10 EC	50	18.96	3.53
Cypermethrin	10 EC	75	19.26	4.42
Permethrin	10 EC	75	7.95	3.41
Fenvalerate	20 EC	75	22.99	3.54
Fenvalerate	20 EC	100	28.78	2.81
Fenvalerate	20 EC	125	27.92	2.99
Fenthion (treated control)	50 EC	500	21.07	2.74
Untreated control	-	-	39.13	1.89
CD (P = 0.05)	-	-	2.00	1.21

All chemical treatments, especially permethrin, checked leaffolders. Plots treated with the 3 synthetic pyrethroids had higher yields than the untreated

control, and plots sprayed with cypermethrin at 75 g a.i./ha yielded more than the treated control (see table).

Field control of yellow stem borer by foliar and granular insecticides in Punjab, India

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The yellow stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker), a serious rice pest in the Ferozepur district of the Punjab, is spreading to other parts of the state. Six spray and five granular formulations at 0.50 and 1.00 kg a.i./ha were tested for yellow stem borer control in 25 m²

Spray and granular formulation control of the yellow stem borer in Punjab, India, 1981.

Treatment ^a	Deadhearts (%) ^b		Whiteheads (%) ^b
	50 DT	70 DT	90 DT
Carbaryl -gamma BHC	2.12 b	7.33 de	3.02 ef
Carbofuran	0.74 a	4.94 bc	1.55 b
Chlorpyrifos	1.67 b	4.90 ab	0.71 a
Fenitrothion	11.32 f	10.33 f	3.65 ef
Gamma BHC	4.58 c	6.13 cd	3.29 def
Methyl parathion	7.75 de	9.22 ef	3.91 f
Monocrotophos	2.05 b	9.23 ef	1.55 bc
Phorate	1.93 b	3.70 ab	1.41 ab
Phosalone	8.55	9.44 ef	2.43 cde
Phosphamidon	5.02 cd	3.08 a	1.75 bcd
Quinalphos	4.62 cd	8.18 ef	3.62 ef
Control (untreated check)	15.93 g	16.80 g	12.21 g

^aSpray and granular formulations at 0.50 and 1.00 kg a.i./ha, respectively, were applied at 30, 50, and 70 days after transplanting (DT). ^bMeans followed by a common letter in a column are not significantly different at the 5% level.